

On the Hodgkin-Huxley Equation on a Curve

Aman Chawla

May 24, 2025

Abstract

In this note, the author takes a few steps towards setting up the Hodgkin-Huxley equation, but along a curve. The new formulation has potentially high relevance for realistic modeling of tracts of ephaptically interacting axons.

We begin by recalling the Hodgkin Huxley equation [1, 2, 3] in the following form,

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = \kappa_1 \frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} - \kappa_2 V. \quad (1)$$

Next, we introduce a pair of curves in space and time, $(g(x), h(t))$, along which an axon lies according to the rule,

$$x_{pos} = g(x) \quad (2)$$

and

$$t_{pos} = h(t) \quad (3)$$

where x_{pos} is the spatial location along the axon and t_{pos} is the temporal location at which that spatial location is being considered. Our task is to find the new version of Equation (1). Using the chain rule for differentiation,

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \cdot \frac{\partial g}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial h} \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = 0 + \frac{\partial V}{\partial h} \cdot \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} \quad (4)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \cdot \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial V}{\partial h} \frac{\partial h}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \cdot \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} + 0. \quad (5)$$

Thus,

$$\frac{\partial^2 V}{\partial x^2} = \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \cdot \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \right] = \frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \right] \cdot \frac{\partial g}{\partial x}. \quad (6)$$

Thus,

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial h} \cdot \frac{\partial h}{\partial t} = \kappa_1 \left[\frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \cdot \frac{\partial^2 g}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \right] \cdot \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} \right] - \kappa_2 V. \quad (7)$$

Consider the case that

$$g(x) = \cos x \quad (8)$$

and

$$h(t) = t. \quad (9)$$

That is, the axon “snakes” along a cosinusoidal path. In this case, the Hodgkin Huxley equation becomes,

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial h} = -\kappa_1 \left[\cos x \cdot \frac{\partial V}{\partial g} + \sin x \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left[\frac{\partial V}{\partial g} \right] \right] - \kappa_2 V. \quad (10)$$

The study of ephaptic coupling in tracts of such axons [4], in three dimensions, with tortuosity [5] and so on, becomes an entirely different, but related, line of study, with potential high relevance to realistic modeling. In particular, the tortuosity formulation can be made much richer when each infinitesimal segment is of this form.

References

- [1] B Frankenhaeuser and AF Huxley. The action potential in the myelinated nerve fibre of xenopus laevis as computed on the basis of voltage clamp data. *The Journal of Physiology*, 171(2):302, 1964.
- [2] Alan Lloyd Hodgkin and Andrew Fielding Huxley. Propagation of electrical signals along giant nerve fibres. *Proceedings of the Royal Society of London. Series B-Biological Sciences*, 140(899):177–183, 1952.
- [3] Alan L Hodgkin and Andrew F Huxley. A quantitative description of membrane current and its application to conduction and excitation in nerve. *The Journal of physiology*, 117(4):500, 1952.
- [4] Aman Chawla. *On Axon-Axon Interaction via Currents and Fields*. PhD thesis, University of South Florida, 2017.
- [5] Aman Chawla and Salvatore Domenic Morgera. On the geometry of interacting axon tracts in relation to their functional properties. *Commun. Math. Biol. Neurosci.*, 2024:Article–ID, 2024.